

How to Cite (APA): Kose, Y. (2025). A fuzzy inference system based digital maturity model for manufacturing enterprises. In Proceedings of the IMSS'25 (pp. 156–166). Düzce University - Türkiye, 25–27 September 2025.

A Fuzzy Inference System Based Digital Maturity Model for Manufacturing Enterprises

Yildiz Kose¹

¹ Department of Industrial Engineering, Karadeniz Technical University, Trabzon, Turkey
yildizkose@ktu.edu.tr

KEYWORDS - Digital transformation, digital maturity model, fuzzy rule based, wood based panel production.

ABSTRACT

Digital maturity models are essential tools for assessing an organization's readiness, capability, and progress in adopting digital technologies. These models support strategic decision-making by identifying current digital capabilities and guiding digital transformation efforts. However, existing digital maturity models often rely on rigid and limited perspectives and linear scoring systems that fail to capture the vagueness and subjectivity inherent in real-world organizational assessments. To address this gap, this study proposes a novel digital maturity assessment framework based on a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS), which enables the incorporation of expert judgment and uncertainty in a structured and systematic way. To develop the model, key input dimensions of smart manufacturing ecosystem, Factory 4.0, Logistics 4.0, Operator 4.0, and Management 4.0 were identified based on an extensive literature review and expert consultation. The output variable was defined as the organization's overall digital maturity level, categorized into distinct stages ranging from Outsider to Top Leader. A comprehensive rule base was established using expert knowledge, and the fuzzy inference process was implemented through the Mamdani approach. The model was tested in a company engaged in wood-based panel production. The findings highlight uneven digital maturity across departments and confirm that high Factory 4.0 and Logistics 4.0 levels are necessary but not sufficient; further progress depends on advancing Operator 4.0 and Management 4.0 as well.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the era of rapid technological advancement, digital technologies have become a fundamental driver of organizational transformation, enabling firms to digitize core production processes, enhance operational efficiency, achieve rapid returns, and realize strategic objectives [1,2]. Many firms are advancing in their Industry 4.0 journey by leveraging the benefits of digitalization [3]. However, new ways of creating value through digital transformation are still being explored, and emerging technologies continue to evolve [2]. The pursuit of digital transformation continues to present new challenges, as firms strive to unlock value through emerging technologies and adapt their operations accordingly. Adapting operations to these new technologies often involves complex processes and substantial financial investment. To effectively manage this transformation, companies need to gain a comprehensive perspective on their level of digital maturity. Digital transformation maturity models

provide organizations with a structured means to assess their alignment with Industry 4.0 and digital technologies throughout the digitalization process [1,4]. These models help identify gaps in transformation efforts, define improvement initiatives, and enable companies to self-assess their current state of digital maturity. As technological and digital transformation progresses, the demand for digital maturity models is expected to grow steadily.

Gökalp and Martinez [3] provided a comprehensive and structured approach for assessing digital transformation process capabilities. The model is highly process-oriented and may not provide sufficient flexibility for application across diverse sectors with varying transformation dynamics. Cinar et al.'s study proposes a modular I4.0 maturity model and framework integrating four key dimensions: Factory 4.0, Logistics 4.0, Management 4.0, and Operator 4.0, and applies them in a case study with technology forecasting [4]. Akdil et al. proposed a new Industry 4.0 maturity model with three key dimensions services, strategy and organization, and smart processes/products and four maturity levels, aiming to help companies assess their transformation readiness. Their model emphasizes managerial and organizational alignment, yet it could be enhanced by incorporating more detailed operational and technological dimensions [5]. Sjödin et al. analyzed the challenges of implementing smart factories through in-depth case studies of five factories from two leading automotive manufacturers. Based on the findings, a preliminary smart factory maturity model is proposed, built around three key principles: cultivating digital talent, enabling agile processes, and deploying modular technologies [6]. In addition to the ones detailed above, many maturity models have been developed in the literature to provide comprehensive guidance and a roadmap for improvement to organizations [7,8].

Assessing digital maturity presents several challenges, including subjectivity in stakeholder perceptions, lack of standardized metrics, and the complexity of evaluating multiple interrelated domains such as technology, processes, and leadership [6]. Rapid technological change can quickly render assessment models outdated, while data quality and availability often limit accuracy. Additionally, many models struggle with scalability across different sectors and integration into strategic decision-making. Furthermore, most digital maturity models rely on a single-perspective approach, often focusing solely on technology or organizational aspects. To address these issues, hybrid approaches combining fuzzy logic is recommended for more reliable and adaptable assessments in a multi-dimensional perspective.

Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) provides a robust and flexible methodological framework for modeling complex, multi-dimensional, and linguistically expressed phenomena such as digital maturity [9]. Given that digital transformation involves subjective judgments, expert opinions, and qualitative assessments particularly when evaluating intangible factors like organizational culture, technological capability, or leadership readiness FIS allows for the effective incorporation of imprecise or vague input data through linguistic variables. The Mamdani-type FIS, in particular, is well-suited for such contexts due to its interpretability and rule-based structure, which closely mirrors human reasoning. By translating expert knowledge into a set of fuzzy if-then rules, FIS facilitates a structured yet adaptable evaluation process that accommodates uncertainty and gradation in input values. Therefore, FIS serves as a scientifically grounded decision-support tool for organizations aiming to assess and improve their digital maturity in alignment with Industry 4.0 paradigms. FIS have been applied to evaluate different dimensions of organizational and technological maturity, including the leanness of manufacturing cells [10], the digital readiness of operations and supply chain management [9], the maturity of sales and operations planning processes [11], and the technical interoperability level of e-government systems [12].

Unlike previous FIS-based studies that focused on specific functional areas such as manufacturing leanness, supply chain readiness, sales and operations planning, or e-government interoperability, this study adopts a holistic perspective on organizational digital transformation. The proposed FIS-based model integrates core Industry 4.0 dimensions—namely Factory 4.0, Logistics 4.0, Operator 4.0, and Management 4.0—into a comprehensive framework that employs fuzzy logic to capture gradations in digital capabilities. In this context, the FIS offers a realistic yet simplified

representation of complex manufacturing and supply chain environments, where uncertainty and vagueness are inherent. It enables the modeling of non-linear relationships through fuzzy if-then rules that reflect the qualitative aspects of expert knowledge. Moreover, its rule-based structure allows for the interpretation of linguistic variables, making it particularly useful in situations where quantitative data are insufficient or too imprecise for statistical analysis. By doing so, the model moves beyond single-domain evaluations and effectively addresses the interdependencies among technological, human, and managerial factors. The use of linguistic variables and fuzzy inference provides a more nuanced and adaptable assessment of an enterprise's digital maturity level. This model is validated through a case study involving participants from the wood-based panel production industry in Turkey, offering empirical evidence of its practical applicability. Overall, the proposed fuzzy approach better accommodates the inherent uncertainty of digital transformation processes than deterministic methods and successfully captures the complexities of real-world industrial systems.

The structure of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 explain the addressed problem. Section 3 details the FIS, Section 4 presents the proposed solution model, Section 5 discusses the findings derived from the case study, and Section 6 concludes the paper by summarizing key outcomes and outlining directions for future research.

2 PROBLEM DEFINITION

In the context of Industry 4.0, assessing an enterprise's digital maturity level is a complex challenge due to the multifaceted and evolving nature of digital transformation. To address this, the present study proposes a maturity evaluation approach that considers four fundamental dimensions of smart manufacturing ecosystem: Factory 4.0, Logistics 4.0, Operator 4.0, and Management 4.0 [4]. The first dimension refers to a decentralized and intelligent production environment characterized by automated systems, real-time monitoring of operations, and seamless cyber-physical integration. It embodies the concept of a smart factory, where interconnected processes continuously generate data that is utilized to enhance adaptability and responsiveness to dynamic production requirements [6]. Factory 4.0 includes some technologies such as digital twin, additive manufacturing, and machine to machine communication. Logistics 4.0 refers to smart supply chain management that enables end-to-end visibility, responsiveness and digital transformation of existing business processes [2,4,13,14]. This dimension related to autonomous material handling, real time tracking, and digital integration with the supplier. Operator 4.0 focuses on human-cyber-physical systems designed to enhance human-machine collaboration. Within the Industry 4.0 paradigm, the Operator 4.0 embodies a smart and adaptive workforce, equipped with digital and cognitive tools that enhance human-machine collaboration and support continuous learning in dynamic production environments [4,15]. These technologies can be listed as augmented reality, virtual reality, wearable technologies, and human-machine interface. Management 4.0 incorporates strategic approaches required to adapt to modern industrial challenges such as shorter product life cycles, dynamic value chains, and the need for cost-effective and sustainable production. Such investments should be complemented by a strategic alignment of the organization's vision and governance structures [16]. Therefore, the inclusion of these dimensions within the digital maturity evaluation model is both theoretically justified and practically relevant for capturing the multifaceted requirements of successful digital transformation.

Based on these dimensions, digital maturity levels are categorized into five hierarchical classes: Top Performer, Experienced, Intermediate, Beginner, and Outsider. A Top Performer is characterized by comprehensive adoption and seamless integration of Industry 4.0 technologies. Experienced organizations have adopted advanced digital practices but may not yet be fully optimized. Intermediate enterprises show moderate progress with partial implementation of digital capabilities. The Beginner level reflects limited efforts and early-stage digital initiatives, whereas Outsider indicates minimal or no engagement with digital transformation. This stratified approach enables a clearer differentiation between varying degrees of digital capability and readiness, allowing decision-makers to identify where their organization stands within the Industry 4.0 continuum. Such

categorization enhances the model's diagnostic value by translating fuzzy and qualitative assessments into meaningful managerial insights. It also facilitates benchmarking across organizations and sectors, supports the formulation of targeted improvement strategies, and helps prioritize resource allocation for digital initiatives. In essence, this hierarchical classification not only simplifies the interpretation of fuzzy outputs but also strengthens the model's practical relevance for strategic planning and continuous improvement.

3 FUZZY INFERENCE SYSTEM

Fuzzy Inference Systems (FISs) enable the integration of a knowledge base into evaluation models, using linguistic terms to support decision-making in a way that mimics human reasoning. This feature is especially useful in scenarios where subjective judgment plays a significant role, as in this study. Building such a knowledge base involves: (a) defining linguistic terms that segment the fuzzy input and output variables, and (b) formulating "if-then" rules that determine the output labels based on combinations of input labels [17]. The rule base should cover all possible conditions and must also remain consistent. The output value corresponding to a given input is determined based on how the knowledge is modeled. This process constitutes inference and decision-making. Two or more logical statements are combined using logical connectors such as AND and OR. Some of the main methods used in the inference stage includes Mamdani, Larsen, Takagi-Sugeno-Kang, and Tsukamoto [18]. The Mamdani technique is also referred to as the max-min method in the literature. In this approach, the min and max operators are used together during the decision-making process. The general form of the IF-THEN structure in the Mamdani fuzzy model's rule base is given in the following equation.

$$\text{IF } a_1 A_{i1} \text{ and } a_2 A_{i2} \text{ and } \dots a_r A_{ir} \text{ THEN } b B_i, \quad i=1,2,\dots,k \quad (1)$$

where, a_s ($s=1,2,\dots,r$) is input, A_{is} and B_i are linguistic terms defined membership functions, b is output value, and k is the number of rules. The intersections of these inputs and their corresponding membership functions can result in fuzzy values. Due to the AND logical operator between the antecedents in the first rule, the minimum membership values can be selected for each rule. Then, the maximum value of the intersecting triangles provides a single membership value as the output. The aggregated values from the discrete sets of rules and the defuzzified value y^* are yielded. When employing the Mamdani fuzzy inference technique, the output of the inference process is typically represented as a fuzzy set. To enable practical interpretation and application of these results, this fuzzy output must be transformed into a single crisp value through a defuzzification process. The Mamdani method often utilizes the Centroid (Center of Gravity) technique as the primary defuzzification approach, which calculates the center of the area under the aggregated output membership function. This approach is favored for its ability to reflect the distribution of membership values across the output range. Other defuzzification methods such as Mean of Maximum, Bisector of Area, or Smallest/Largest of Maximum may also be applied depending on the shape and characteristics of the membership functions [18]. Defuzzification in the Mamdani model is a critical step to convert the linguistically-expressed reasoning into actionable, quantitative decisions.

4 MAMDANI FUZZY INFERENCE SYSTEM FOR DIGITAL MATURTY MODEL

The digital maturity model enables an enterprise to assess its current state in the digital transformation journey and to identify areas for improvement, thereby supporting the development of a strategic roadmap. A classical digital maturity model typically consists of five steps: (i) identifying process, (ii) determining evaluation forms, (iii) assessing process and sub-process, (iv)

comparing control measures, and (v) monitoring and reviewing. Although digital maturity assessment inherently involves subjectivity and uncertainty, many models in the literature rely on classical set theory which can result in information loss. For this reason, using a fuzzy logic approach, which is commonly applied in the literature for processing linguistic data, allows for more reliable outcomes when determining the level of digital maturity. In addition, the proposed model is built on the understanding that digital transformation is not a standalone process but is influenced by multiple interrelated factors. The digital maturity level obtained from the proposed model is evaluated through four main dimensions: Factory 4.0, Operator 4.0, Logistics 4.0, and Management 4.0. The step-by-step description of the proposed methodology is given as follows.

Stage 1. Define the input variables: In the first stage of the proposed methodology, the input variables that influence the digital maturity of an enterprise are identified. These variables represent key components of the smart manufacturing ecosystem and are structured under four main dimensions: Factory 4.0, Operator 4.0, Logistics 4.0, and Management 4.0. Each dimension consists of specific criteria that reflect critical technological, organizational, and operational capabilities. The fundamentals of input factors are given in Section 2. Summarily, Factory 4.0 includes smart manufacturing systems and real-time data monitoring, while Operator 4.0 covers human-machine interaction, digital skills, and occupational safety. Logistics 4.0 focuses on automation, traceability, and integrated supply chains, whereas Management 4.0 addresses strategic alignment, leadership commitment, and data-driven decision-making. The company's evaluations from the employee according to the dimensions are collected on a scale between 0 and 10 points. The obtained evaluations are processed in a fuzzy logic-based system and the outputs are obtained in the same way. As a result, the digital maturity level of the company is determined. According to the given answer, the range of the relevant dimension is determined based on Table 1.

Table 1 Linguistic Terms and Fuzzy Numbers for Input Factors

Score	Linguistic terms	Triangular fuzzy numbers
$1 < \text{score} \leq 4$	Low-L	(0, 3, 5)
$4 < \text{score} \leq 6$	Medium-M	(3, 5, 7)
$6 < \text{score}$	High-H	(5, 7, 10)

The membership degree of inputs is determined according to Figure 1. Three clusters are defined as "Low (L), Medium (M), High (H)". The range of the given answer should be determined and the cluster it belongs to should be determined from here. Based on the graph, the membership degree of the given answer and which cluster it is a member of, in other words, the degree of belonging to the cluster, is determined. In addition, membership functions have been obtained for all dimensions.

Figure 1: Membership Functions for Input Linguistic Terms

Stage 2. Define the output variables: In the second stage of the methodology, the output variables representing digital maturity levels are defined. These variables serve as the evaluation result of the FIS and reflect the enterprise's position in its digital transformation journey. The maturity levels are classified into five distinct linguistic categories: Outsider, Beginner, Intermediate, Experienced, and Top Performer. Each category is represented by a triangular fuzzy number. Table 2 presents the linguistic terms and their corresponding fuzzy numbers used to model the output variable in the system. Membership degrees of triangular numbers are given in Figure 2.

Table 2 Linguistic terms and corresponding fuzzy numbers for output

Level	Output label	Fuzzy numbers
$Level \leq 2$	Outsider	(0, 2, 4)
$2 < Level \leq 4$	Beginner	(2, 4, 6)
$4 < Level \leq 6$	Intermediate	(3, 5, 7)
$6 < Level \leq 8$	Experienced	(4, 6, 8)
$8 < Level$	Top performer	(6, 8, 10)

Figure 2: Membership Functions for Digital Maturity

The use of fuzzy numbers ensures a gradual transition between levels rather than rigid classification, enabling more realistic and human-like reasoning in the assessment process. This fuzzy representation facilitates a more robust and adaptive assessment of maturity levels, accommodating the inherent uncertainty and subjectivity involved in digital transformation evaluations.

Stage 3. Determine fuzzy rule based: In this phase, a comprehensive fuzzy rule base is constructed to represent the relationships between input variables and the corresponding digital maturity levels. The model considers four key dimensions of digital transformation, Factory 4.0, Logistics 4.0, Operator 4.0, and Management 4.0, each evaluated linguistically using three terms: Low (L), Medium (M), and High (H). Given that each input can take one of three linguistic values, the total number of possible input combinations is eighty-one. A fuzzy rule is defined in the form:

IF Factory 4.0 is X AND Logistics 4.0 is Y AND Operator 4.0 is Z AND Management 4.0 is W THEN Maturity is Level

where, X , Y , Z , and W are linguistic labels of corresponding input factors. The output levels are selected from the predefined fuzzy categories: Outsider, Beginner, Intermediate, Experienced, and Top Performer. The rule assignment logic is based on the distribution of input levels (L, M, H) in each combination. For instance, combinations with a high concentration of 'H' inputs are assigned higher maturity levels. Combinations with predominantly 'L' values are assigned lower maturity levels. Mixed combinations are evaluated proportionally using heuristic rules to reflect nuanced maturity levels.

Stage 4. Defuzzification of the Final Aggregate: In this stage, the defuzzification process is applied to convert the aggregated fuzzy output into a crisp value that represents the final digital maturity score. The Centroid method is adopted due to its interpretability and balanced representation of the fuzzy set.

This method calculates the defuzzified value z^* by determining the “center of mass” of the area under the aggregated fuzzy membership function, as shown below:

$$z^* = \frac{\int z \mu(z) dz}{\int \mu(z) dz} \quad (2)$$

where $\mu(z)$ is the membership degree at output level z .

This technique is particularly suitable for triangular fuzzy numbers and continuous fuzzy distributions. It ensures that the final crisp score is sensitive to the shape and spread of the fuzzy output, rather than being overly influenced by extreme values or dominant categories.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A case study was designed to test the proposed digital maturity model. The digital maturity assessment was conducted in a company based in Türkiye that specializes in wood based panel production. Employees from different departments evaluated the company's level of digital transformation based on four distinct factors using a structured questionnaire. In total, 20 employees participated in the assessment. The levels of the defined factors were rated by employees using the scale provided in Table 1. The four factors rated by each employee were processed through the FIS model, and the digital maturity level of the company was determined individually for each respondent. The frequency distribution of digital maturity levels, based on employees' ratings of the input factors and their corresponding FIS outputs, is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Frequency of Assessed Digital Maturity Levels

Figure 3 illustrates the frequency distribution of employees' perceptions of the company's digital maturity level, as derived from the FIS-based evaluation. The results indicate a relatively balanced distribution across all five maturity levels, Beginner, Experienced, Intermediate, Outsider, and Top Performer with the highest frequency (4 responses each) observed in the Experienced, Intermediate, Outsider, and Top Performer categories. The Beginner level was slightly less common, with three employees selecting this category. This suggests that employee perceptions of the company's digital maturity are highly diverse, reflecting differences in departmental practices, roles, or exposure to digital initiatives. Notably, the presence of both low (Beginner, Outsider) and high (Top Performer) classifications highlights potential inconsistencies in digital transformation across organizational units. These findings support the importance of a multidimensional assessment framework and suggest that further alignment is needed to achieve a more cohesive digital maturity profile.

One of the surface map scenarios aligned with the model was implemented. These maps are used to visually understand the relationship between two input variables and one output variable, making the system's behavior more intuitive. To observe the combined effect of production and logistics digitalization on the digital maturity level, a surface map was generated, as shown in Figure 4. The variables Operator 4.0 and Management 4.0 were held constant during this analysis.

Figure 4: Surface map, Factory 4.0 vs Logistics 4.0

The upward trend observed in the surface map indicates that digital maturity increases as the levels of Factory 4.0 and Logistics 4.0 rise. This confirms the positive contribution of these two variables to digital maturity. At low Factory 4.0 scores (between 0 and 4), the maturity level remains relatively low (approximately between 2 and 3), suggesting that when Factory 4.0 is very limited, overall digital maturity is also constrained. This highlights Factory 4.0 as a critical threshold factor. When Logistics 4.0 values are high on their own (e.g., between 8 and 10), but Factory 4.0 remains low, the resulting digital maturity score still tends to be low. However, when high Logistics 4.0 levels are accompanied by equally high Factory 4.0 levels, the maturity score increases significantly. This indicates that the contribution of logistics infrastructure to digital transformation becomes effective only when integrated with a sufficiently advanced production infrastructure. Additionally, the surface map shows that in some regions, the digital maturity score begins to plateau around a value of 6. This suggests that the combined contribution of Factory 4.0 and Logistics 4.0 may be limited beyond a certain point, and that further increases in maturity may depend on other variables such as Operator 4.0 and Management 4.0.

6 CONCLUSION

Assessing digital maturity is a subjective process shaped by expert judgment, which can vary across individuals. Although existing guides offer structured criteria, they often fail to address the ambiguity in real-world evaluations. By leveraging normalization techniques and AI-based systems, expert opinions can be translated into measurable and consistent data. This study addresses these limitations by proposing a FIS-based model that systematically incorporates expert knowledge and handles uncertainty more effectively than traditional scoring methods. This study proposed and implemented a Mamdani-type FIS to evaluate the digital maturity of organizations based on key Industry 4.0 dimensions. A case study was conducted in a wood-based panel industry company in Turkey to demonstrate the applicability and effectiveness of the model. Employees assessed the organization using four input dimensions such as Factory 4.0, Logistics 4.0, Operator 4.0, and Management 4.0 which were processed through the FIS model to determine their perception of the organization's digital maturity.

Although digital maturity assessment models are increasingly being explored in the context of Industry 4.0, many existing approaches lack the flexibility to handle subjective, expert-driven input, especially in organizational environments where digital transformation is non-uniform. Most maturity models rely on static scoring methods or survey-based checklists that fail to capture fuzziness and human perception. This study addresses that gap by offering a fuzzy logic-based evaluation method capable of modeling uncertainty and incorporating linguistic variables into decision-making. The integration of Mamdani-type FIS for digital maturity assessment introduces a novel, human-centered evaluation approach that accommodates subjective inputs and varying departmental conditions. Additionally, the focus on underexplored sectors like particleboard production industry contributes to filling the empirical gap in sector-specific digital transformation research.

The results revealed a relatively even distribution of digital maturity levels across the organization. While several employees rated the company at the Intermediate or Experienced level, others perceived it as being at the extremes either as Beginners or even Top Performers. This spread indicates that perceptions of digital transformation vary considerably across departments or roles, rather than clustering around a single maturity tier. These differences underscore the need for a more unified digital strategy to minimize disparities in digital capability and access. The proposed model demonstrated its effectiveness in capturing these nuanced perceptions and translating them into actionable insights that can guide targeted improvements in the company's digital transformation journey. The fuzzy inference approach proved suitable for modeling qualitative assessments and aggregating them into a coherent maturity score. Factory 4.0 is a stronger determinant of digital maturity, while Logistics 4.0 plays a complementary and supportive role. However, the level of maturity achievable through these two factors alone is limited; attaining higher levels of maturity

requires organizational and human-centered transformation, particularly through Operator 4.0 and Management 4.0.

Overall, the FIS-based model provides a flexible, intuitive, and decision-supportive tool for organizations seeking to evaluate and enhance their digital transformation journeys across multiple dimensions. The proposed model can serve as a decision-support tool for managers and policymakers, helping them to identify digital gaps, prioritize interventions, and track progress over time.

In future studies, each main dimension can be further decomposed into sub-dimensions. Integrating these sub criteria into the FIS would enhance the model's precision and reliability by grounding it in a more rigorous scientific methodology.

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by Office of Scientific Research Projects of Karadeniz Technical University. Project number: FBA-2024-15827

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